

E4.5 Final prototype for zero-touch and proactive network management

**Fecha de Publicación:
30/09/2024**

[6GENABLERS-AI]
[6GENABLERS]

Programa de Universalización de Infraestructuras Digitales para la Cohesión - 6G I+D

Financiado por la Unión Europea
NextGenerationEU

GOBIERNO
DE ESPAÑA

Plan de Recuperación,
Transformación
y Resiliencia

Paquete de Trabajo (PT)	PT3
Líder del PT	i2CAT
Editor Principal	Juan Sebastian Camargo
Contribuyentes	Hatim Chergui, Shuaib Siddiqui
Nivel de diseminación	PU
Tipo	RE

Nivel de diseminación

PU	Publico
PP	Restringido a otros participantes del programa
RE	Restringido a un grupo especificado por el consorcio
CO	Confidencial solo para miembros del consorcio

Tipo

PR	Prototipo
RE	Reporte
SP	Especificación
TO	Herramienta
OT	Otro

Histórico de versiones del documento				
versión	Autor	Estado	Fecha	Comentarios
v1.0	Juan Sebastian Camargo		30/09/2024	

Table of Contents

Table of Contents.....	3
List of Tables.....	4
List of Figures.....	5
List of Acronyms.....	6
1 Introduction.....	7
2 Logical description.....	8
3 Configuration.....	10
4 Usage.....	12
5 Conclusion.....	13

List of Figures

Figure 1 Communication between the feature store and the data acquisition for ML.....8

Figure 2 Communication between the AIOPS OPNEB and the model AI Exposure.....9

Figure 3 Data obtained from the Feature Store and used for the training.....12

List of Acronyms

3D	Three Dimension
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AIOps	AI Operations
AR	Augmented Reality
CD	Continuous Delivery
CI	Continuous Integration
6DoF	Six Degrees of Freedom
FPS	Frame per Second
HD	High Definition
HTC	Holographic-Type Communications
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
MEC	Multi-access Edge Computing
ML	Machine Learning
MLOps	Machine Learning Operations
NFV	Network Function Virtualization
NR	New Radio
QoE	Quality of Experience
RAN	Radio Access Network
SoA	State-of-the-Art
TD	Technological Domain
UE	User Equipment
UNICO	Universalización de Infraestructuras Digitales para la Cohesión
VNF	Virtual Network Function
VR	Virtual Reality
XR	Extended Reality

1 Introduction

The final phase of the prototyping for zero-touch and proactive network management is the successful integration of the Feature Store with the Kubeflow Pipelines Data Acquisition module. This critical step ensures that we could efficiently acquire and process the necessary data to support and train our machine learning model. Once the data acquisition is complete, we implement a data cleaning process to eliminate irrelevant or redundant information, thereby improving the quality and reliability of our dataset.

Following the data cleaning, we establish an automation process designed to enable the neural networks to dynamically adapt to the varying number of input features. This adaptability is essential for optimizing network performance and responsiveness, allowing our system to use data effectively. By automating these processes, we not only streamline our workflow but also position our network management solution to respond proactively to emerging conditions and challenges.

In this deliverable we are going to describe how the data integration, processing and cleaning is done. Additionally, we will describe the automation of the neural network inputs and the exposure of the trained model using an API call.

2 Logical description

In the previously described Kubeflow pipelines, the integration of a feature store with a data acquisition step is key for achieving robust and efficient model development. The data acquisition phase is responsible for gathering and ingesting raw data from various sources, which is then transformed into actionable features within the feature store. This synergy ensures that the features derived from the acquired data are not only relevant and high-quality but also standardized and reusable across different models.

By using a feature store in conjunction with the data acquisition step, it is possible to streamline the feature engineering process, significantly reducing the time and effort required to prepare data for training. This combination not only accelerates the development cycle but also ensures that models are built on consistent, high-quality features, leading to improved accuracy and performance in the needed environments.

As part of the previously defined architecture, the data acquisition module from the Kubeflow Pipeline will communicate with the feature-store directly, as can be seen in Figure 1.

Figure 1 Communication between the feature store and the data acquisition for ML.

The final step in the model lifecycle involves deploying the trained model and sharing its predictions or outputs with the relevant governing entity, in this case with OPNEB's AIOPS. This stage is technically critical as it closes the loop between model development and application, ensuring that the insights generated by the model are actionable and can drive decision-making actions.

Figure 2 Communication between the AIOPS OPNEB and the model AI Exposure.

Once deployed, the model is exposed via an API (Application Programming Interface), allowing other applications or services to interact with it. RESTful APIs are commonly used for this purpose, enabling other entities to send data for inference and receive predictions in a standardized format. This integration facilitates seamless communication between the model and the rest of the entities in the system.

3 Configuration

The architecture includes a data acquisition layer that continuously collects raw data from various sources. This data is ingested into the system and processed into features stored in the Feature Store. This process ensures that the ML model has access to the most up-to-date and relevant data for training. The `obtain_dataset` function automates the process of retrieving, processing, and saving a dataset within a Kubeflow pipeline. It handles data acquisition from, performs necessary preprocessing steps such as scaling, and stores the prepared data for subsequent stages of the machine learning workflow.

```
def obtain_dataset(X_full_artifact: Output[Dataset], y_full_artifact:
Output[Dataset]):

    url = "http://feature-store-service-internal.local:8080/v2/clone_repo"

    headers = {

        "Content-Type": "application/json"

    }

    data = {

        "feature.py": "https://gitlab/raw/main/feature.py",

        "feature_store.yaml": "https://gitlab.com//raw/main/feature_store.yaml"

    }

    file_content = requests.post(url, headers=headers, data=json.dumps(data))

    if file_content:

        decoded_content = file_content.decode('utf-8') # Adjust encoding if necessary

        df = pd.read_csv(io.StringIO(decoded_content))

        np.save("/tmp/x_train.npy", X_full)

        os.rename("/tmp/x_train.npy", X_full_artifact.path)

        np.save("/tmp/y_train.npy", y_full)

        os.rename("/tmp/y_train.npy", y_full_artifact.path)
```

Additionally, it is possible to include a feature that is capable of adapt the input of the neural network according with the features obtained from the Feature Store. Having a neural network that can adapt to different numbers of feature inputs offers several advantages that improves its versatility and effectiveness. This adaptability enables the model to handle varying data scenarios without requiring extensive reconfiguration, making it suitable for dynamic environments where feature availability can change. This

flexibility facilitates the integration of new data sources or features, allowing the model to use additional information for improved predictions.

```
response_post_features = requests.post(post_url, headers=headers, json=data)

def obtain_dataset(X_full_artifact: Output[Dataset], y_full_artifact: Output[Dataset],
num_features_artifact: Output[int]):

    if response_post_features.status_code == 200:
        offline_features = response_post_features.json()

    if response_post_features == 200:
        decoded_content = response_post_features.content.decode('utf-8')
        df = pd.read_csv(io.StringIO(decoded_content))
        n_features = df.shape[1] # Get the number of features (columns)
        num_features_artifact.set(n_features)
```

4 Usage

By using this snippet in conjunction with the other previously explained code (For more information please refer to deliverable “E3.5 Intermediate prototype of the inclusion of AIOps in the system”) we are able to obtain the data from the Feature Store, with its corresponding acknowledgement:

```
[{'container_cpu_time': 0.4078509091,
  'container_cpu_utilization': 0.0023405235,
  'deployment': 'dummy-python-deployment',
  'event_date': '2024-08-02',
  'event_time': '14:00:00',
  'event_timestamp': 1722607200000,
  'k8s_pod_cpu_time': 0.394327,
  'k8s_pod_cpu_utilization': 0.0007106301,
  'k8s_pod_network_io': 10485.5454545455}]
```

Figure 3 Data obtained from the Feature Store and used for the training.

In the obtained data, several fields are not required for training the model because they do not contribute useful features for the prediction process. Specifically, the fields *event_date*, *event_time*, and *event_timestamp* are used to classify the events chronologically, but since the model does not include any time series features or temporal dependencies, these fields are unnecessary. Including them would not provide any meaningful value for the model's predictive capabilities and could even introduce noise. Therefore, for the purposes of model training, we will exclude these fields to focus on the relevant numerical metrics that can influence the outcomes we want to predict.

5 Conclusion

We have successfully integrated and installed the Kubeflow Pipelines in a cloud architecture. Additionally, we have successfully acquired and processed the essential data. Furthermore, by performing a data cleaning process we have enhanced the model's quality and reliability, ensuring that the model is trained on the most relevant information. Our implementation of an automation process allows the neural networks to dynamically adjust to varying numbers of input features. This flexibility is crucial for optimizing network performance and responsiveness, enabling our system to effectively utilize incoming data and adapt to evolving network conditions. Exposing the trained model through an API call not only streamlines integration with other systems but also facilitates real-time decision-making capabilities.

Collectively, these advancements have streamlined our workflow and positioned our network management solution to proactively address emerging challenges. By embracing automation and adaptability, we have laid the groundwork for a robust system capable of optimizing network operations in an ever-changing technological landscape.